

GINNGER

Brandbook

Brand Identity
Guidelines

V 1.0

GINNUGER will ease the regeneration of neighbourhoods and built environments through the implementation of co-creation processes in heterogeneous stakeholders' structures. This will facilitate the planification and implementation of actions in local environments, leading to a reduction of social, environmental, technological and economic risks thus to deliver healthy, affordable and sustainable built environments in EU.

GINNUGER's visual identity took inspiration from the world of miniatures and mini-buildings. The key aspect that triggered this connection was the topic of neighborhoods, small parts of cities with their own structures, people, cultures, attitudes and behavior. All these elements fuse together and create an environment where people understand and help each other, where everyone feels safe and at home. It's a relatively small area, but it is still a part of the world.

That's when the concept was born. Neighborhoods are just a miniature in our world but, thanks to their integrity and their ability to connect people, have the potential to become new realities and tendencies for many other world areas.

Especially with GINNUGER's methodologies, tested in six small areas, new lifestyles and realities could be developed for a better community and for an improved cities infrastructure efficiency.

Visual identity's main traits:

Miniature

Development

Empowerment

N

BRAND PERSONALITY

Unconventional								Institutional
Popular								Niche
Practical								Imaginative
Formal								Casual
Exciting								Reassuring
Sophisticated								Essential
Heart-Oriented								Brain-Oriented
	Definitely	Quite	Slightly	Neutral	Slightly	Quite	Definitely	

POSITIVE LOGO

3

GINNUNGER

HORIZONTAL LOGO

f

GINN GER

GINNUNGER

GINNUNGER

MONOCHROME LOGO

6

LOGO CONSTRUCTION

61 x 15 mm 173 x 44 px

23 x 24 mm 66 x 67 px

13 x 15 mm 36 x 45 px

Do not change the weight of the icon's lines

On a darker background, the only available version of the logo is the negative one, where the icon's colors don't change. Always keep the same color scheme in every version.

Don't change the colors of the monochrome logos. They are already studied to be visible in every situation

Don't stretch or modify the logo proportions

Cyan

R	0	C	60
G	216	M	0
B	255	Y	0
#00D8FF		K	0

Magenta

R	255	C	0
G	0	M	90
B	108	Y	30
#FF006C		K	0

Yellow

R	255	C	0
G	210	M	20
B	78	Y	75
#FFD24E		K	0

Black

R	0
G	0
B	0
#000000	

C	0
M	0
Y	0
K	100

White

R	255
G	255
B	255
#FFFFFF	

C	0
M	0
Y	0
K	0

Omniium Thin

abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxy
 ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
 1234567890
 (!#€%&/.|*',?;:)

Omniium Medium

abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxy
 ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
 1234567890
 (!#€%&/.|*',?;:)

Omniium Bold

**abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxy
 ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
 1234567890
 (!#€%&/.|*',?;:)**

Omniium ExtraBold

**abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxy
 ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
 1234567890
 (!#€%&/.|*',?;:)**

House#1

House#2

House#3

Water Ground

Grass Ground

House#4

Building#1

Building#2

Tree#1

Tree#2

Skyscraper#1

Skyscraper#2

Skyscraper#3

Tree#3

People

Buildings

Environment

When searching for images to use as a branding element, always choose some depicting cities and taken from above. It blends perfectly with the concept of miniature and gives an idea of insight in neighborhoods.

The figures from the illustration set can be used to create a map of a city, serving as a pattern or a texture. It can also be used on different backgrounds, but always with a white trace.

It is possible to write sentences over it, but only if closed in opposite squares like this one.

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Latest Update: January 2024

The rules specified in this document are to be considered guidelines to better understand the project and to look at when designing something new, evolving its identity, or even when breaking the rules.

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